

Microcosm for Sonic Mediation Table and Wave Field Synthesis

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1. PROGRAM NOTES

The sonic meditation table is part of the artists extended saxophone practice. It is an inverted soprano saxophone with clamped keys and different mouthpieces attached to the saxophone through a hose for low frequency drone tones. The instrument was inspired by Pauline Oliveros' Deep Listening Practice and Mazen Kerbaj's improvisational trumpet work. For this conference presentation (which could be either carried out live at the conference site or telematically), the sonic meditation table will be augmented by a wave field synthesis installation with live electronics (VCV rack with Max/MSP) also using a spatialization technique called *virtual microphone control* that was developed by the performer.

Fig. 1. Sonic Meditation Table

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2. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The goal of the piece is to create a spatial sound field following Deep Listening Practice. The sonic meditation table will be picked up by several (contact) microphones, which will be spatialized through WFS and superposed with electronic sounds and multichannel nature field recordings from the macro world.

3. PERFORMANCE NOTES

The duration of the improvisational piece is flexible, ideally between 10 and 15 minutes. The wave field synthesis system will be controlled live with foot and hand controllers. The performer will provide a laptop with his electronic synthesis system and DAW with a multichannel sound card to feed into the WFS system. The piece can be performed as an audio-only piece or with a single video projection depicting the macro insect world of New York's Capital District.

Media Link(s)

- Video:<https://vimeo.com/943898400>
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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work is inspired by Pauline Oliveros' Deep Listening Philosophy and I am grateful for having had the opportunity to work closely with her over several years.

ETHICAL STANDARDS

This research was carried out using internal university resources.

REFERENCES

- [1] Braasch, J. (2019) Hyper-specializing on the saxophone using acoustical insight and deep listening skills, Springer, Cham, Switzerland (ISBN 978-3-030-15045-7)
- [2] Braasch, J. (2024) Pauline's World of Virtuosos: Expanded Instruments, Deep Listening, and Stretched Boundaries. In: Improvising across Abilities: Pauline Oliveros and the Adaptive Use Musical Instrument (AUMI consortium, ed.), University of Michigan Press.